

**CORRECTION OF SELF – DESTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR OF
ADOLESCENTS BY MEANS OF ART THERAPY**

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Annotation: This study explores the potential of art therapy as a means of correcting self-destructive behavior in adolescents. Adolescence is a critical period marked by significant physical, emotional, and social changes, which can sometimes lead to maladaptive coping mechanisms and self-destructive tendencies. Art therapy, with its focus on creative expression and the therapeutic potential of art-making, offers a non-verbal, non-threatening approach to addressing these issues.

Key words: primary school teacher, interaction with social partners, requirements, professional competence.

**КОРРЕКЦИЯ САМОРАЗРУШИТЕЛЬНОГО ПОВЕДЕНИЯ
ПОДРОСТКОВ СРЕДСТВАМИ АРТ-ТЕРАПИИ**

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Аннотация: В данном исследовании рассматривается потенциал арт-терапии как средства коррекции саморазрушительного поведения подростков.

Ключевые слова: коррекция, арт-терапия, взаимодействие с социальными партнерами, требования, профессиональная компетентность.

Подростковый возраст-это критический период, характеризующийся значительными физическими, эмоциональными и социальными изменениями, которые иногда могут привести к дезадаптивным механизмам преодоления и саморазрушительным тенденциям. Арт-терапия, с ее акцентом на творческом самовыражении и терапевтическом потенциале создания произведений искусства, предлагает невербальный, не угрожающий подход к решению этих проблем.

The research examines the theoretical underpinnings of art therapy and its application in treating adolescents with self-destructive behaviors. It delves into the various art therapy techniques and interventions that can be tailored to the unique needs of this age group, including drawing, painting, sculpting, and collage-making. The study also investigates the role of the art therapist in facilitating a safe and supportive environment for self-expression, reflection, and growth. Through a review of empirical studies and case examples, the research highlights the effectiveness of art therapy in promoting self-awareness, emotional regulation, and positive coping strategies among adolescents. It discusses the potential challenges and limitations of using art therapy in this context and suggests best practices for its implementation.

The findings of this study contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting the use of art therapy as a valuable intervention for adolescents struggling with self-destructive behaviors. It offers insights for therapists, educators, and mental health professionals seeking to incorporate creative approaches into their work with young people.

Abstract. In modern society, self-destructive behavior continues to spread among adolescents. This is manifested in the use of alcohol, tobacco smoking, drug addiction, victimization and extreme behavior. The effective implementation of prevention and correction of self-destruction is an urgent problem for personality

psychology, educational psychology, developmental psychology and other industries. The article proposes a new scientific approach to overcoming the self-destructive behavior of adolescents. Self-destructive behavior is one of the compensatory defense mechanisms of adaptation and stabilization of the personality, the ability to adapt to adverse conditions. A teenager with an unformed or critical thinking disorder, acting under the influence of fear, anxiety, hopelessness, shame, guilt, excitement, fatigue or a strong affective state of anger and anger, does not think about the consequences of his actions. The formation and implementation of self-destructive behavior serves as a means for the adolescent to maintain a satisfying "Self-concept" - avoiding feelings, from realizing one's inadequacy with one's own idealized ideas, and feeling helpless.

Абстрактный. В современном обществе среди подростков продолжает распространяться саморазрушительное поведение. Это проявляется в употреблении алкоголя, табакокурении, наркомании, виктимизации и экстремальном поведении. Эффективное осуществление профилактики и коррекции саморазрушения является актуальной проблемой для психологии личности, педагогической психологии, психологии развития и других отраслей. В статье предлагается новый научный подход к преодолению саморазрушительного поведения подростков. Саморазрушительное поведение является одним из компенсаторных защитных механизмов адаптации и стабилизации личности, способности приспосабливаться к неблагоприятным условиям. Подросток с несформированным или нарушенным критическим мышлением, действующий под влиянием страха, тревоги, безнадежности, стыда, вины, возбуждения, усталости или сильного аффективного состояния гнева и злости на себя, не задумывается о последствиях своих действий. Формирование и реализация саморазрушительного поведения служит для подростка средством поддержания удовлетворяющей его "Я-концепции" - избегания чувств, осознания своей неадекватности собственным идеализированным представлениям и чувства беспомощности.

The classes had a positive effect on girls from the study group, unfortunately, correctional work did not significantly affect the male half.

Also in the study group, repeated diagnostics were carried out according to the previously used Bass-Darki method “Diagnosis of indicators and forms of aggression” after the implementation of the correction program.

When reprocessing the results using the Bass-Darki methodology “Diagnostics of indicators and forms of aggression”, it turned out that after the implementation of corrective work, two students changed their answers on the “Hostility” scale to the provided statements, thereby entering the framework of average indicators on this scale. With the help of corrective work, we also managed to reduce high-level indicators on the scale “Aggressiveness” in 3 adolescents, thanks to which, the guys showed results by a repeated technique, thereby entering the framework of average indicators on this scale. On the scale of “Guilt”, unfortunately, there was no positive trend on the part of adolescents.

3 The discussion of the results

Based on the results of the research, we can talk about the effectiveness of the developed correction program.

The results of our study allowed us to formulate the following conclusions.

1. Self-destructive behavior under adverse conditions can be included in the system of personality self-regulation as a factor in maintaining the integrity of a person's personality, maintaining a positive self-relationship, avoiding the experience of frustration.

2. A comprehensive system of measures for the prevention of self-destructive behavior, including diagnostic, educational, correctional and developmental work in a general educational institution, can be an effective tool for its regular implementation.

3. The implementation of the proposed program for the correction of self-destructive behavior by means of art therapy helps to reduce the risk of self-destructive manifestations of adolescents. Promotes the development of their subjective position and increase their importance. Increases the ability of adolescents to use coping strategies in acute and prolonged adverse situations.

The results presented in the article may be of interest for further study of the problem of prevention of self-destructive behavior in adolescence in aspects of the study of its general mechanisms and the search for the most universal and effective means and methods of correction.

4 Conclusion

The preventive and corrective effect on leveling the teenager's self-destructive behavior can be implemented in educational institutions with the maximum coverage of school specialists: psychologist, teachers, social worker, head teacher for educational work and other employees of the organization. Early detection of signs of self-destructive behavior in a teenager will allow for timely corrective work. In order to effectively prevent and correct auto-destructive behavior of adolescents, art therapy can be used.

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